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Zero-touch Network Management**

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List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

5G/6G Zero-Touch Networks (ZSM) represent a revolutionary paradigm shift in networking, where autonomous, self-configuring, and self-optimizing networks are realized. Edge computing has gained prominence as a fundamental component of ZSM networks, **enabling efficient resource allocation and dynamic service provisioning** (e.g. VNFs) at the network's edge. Edge infrastructure discovery is a crucial aspect of ZSM, ensuring that the right resources are available when and where they are needed.

This deliverable E2.3 of 6GENABLERS, IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10, hereinafter referred to as 6GENABLERS-AI:

- Describes the **state of the art in the three main research fields on Zero-Touch networks from the perspective of the underlying edge infrastructure enabling technology**, and the deployment of 5G/6G edge services for low and ultra-low latency applications, namely: network management, AI operations and low-latency applications. In this context, the efficient and intelligent orchestration of geographically distributed edge-cloud infrastructures to facilitate the automated management, placement, and scaling of VNFs and SDNs for 5G/6G networks emerges as a pivotal factor in advancing zero-touch network and service development. Other challenges include the improvement of data management to handle a large amount of delay-sensitive data, the improvement of QoS to meet a diverse range of stringent QoS requirements in order to improve quality of experience (QoE), the prediction of network demand to estimate the required network resources, and subsequently to provide optimal resource allocation to handle the local network demand, the management of location awareness to enable the geographically distributed edge servers to infer their own locations and track the location of end users to support location-based services, and the improvement of resource management to optimize network resource utilization for network performance enhancement due to the limited network resources available in the edge as compared to the cloud.
- Includes an **analysis of requirements from the project use case about Holoportation report (6GENABLERS_SP1_E2.1) and the ETSI Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) reports** related to cloud-edge infrastructure automatic deployment (A2.1) and service orchestration (A2.2). OpenNebula fits within the Management Domain component in the ETSI reference architecture for Zero-touch network and service management (ZSM), providing virtual, physical and edge resource deployment and management. It also provides support for Domain Analytics and Domain Intelligence, enabling the implementation of Closed-Loop Automation and Artificial Intelligence-based Network and Service Automation.
- Describes the **gaps within the current state-of-the-art edge infrastructure technologies, aiming to meet the requirements of zero-touch networks within the scope of the project**. The main challenge arises from the inherently distributed nature of the holoportation application which spawns multiple locations in the cloud-edge continuum. The automatic deployment and configuration of such infrastructures needs to develop robust selection algorithms for the edge-cloud locations, as well as the orchestration capabilities needed to deploy a complex system in an autonomous manner.

- Proposes an **architecture (CE5G) of a Cloud-Edge system designed for edge applications**. The system is presented in a generic form to accommodate a wide range of applications with strong latency requirements. The overall architecture aligns with the requirements discussed in the report, and it is compatible with the zero touch network and service management (ZSM) framework under development by the ETSI organization.
- Discusses the **deployment of the holographic teleportation applications in the CE5G architecture** described above.

1. Introduction

In the market, there are various cloud-edge management tools that offer the capability to combine infrastructure elements in a private data center (private cloud) with resources from a public cloud provider (multi-cloud) or resources at the edge (cloud-edge infrastructure). Examples of these tools include OpenStack StarlingX [MAOY22], which proposes edge extensions based on complex nodes with a large number of microservices, and KubeEdge [X SXH18], which treats each edge server as a cloud node, simplifying management but limiting optimization possibilities and, in this specific case, favoring containers over virtualization. None of these tools allows for programmatic infrastructure definition; instead, they rely on manual deployment to build the platform.

In traditional infrastructure deployment management, different software components (databases, web servers, firewalls, etc.) are integrated to provide a service. The need for manual interventions in change or event management and the ability to separate infrastructure from different development teams have led to the emergence of DevOps and Site Reliability Engineering (SRE) paradigms [BJPM16]. This new approach to Infrastructure as Code (IaC) is based on applying traditional software engineering techniques to infrastructure management, using tools to programmatically deploy, monitor, and manage platform changes [Mo16].

Infrastructure as Code is often referred to as programmable infrastructure or software-defined infrastructure [WBF20]. The most widely used tool for coding Infrastructure as Code platforms is Terraform [Ho22]. Terraform enables the creation, modification, and versioning of any cloud and/or on-premises resource using human-readable configuration files that can be reused and shared, allowing the same workflow to manage different providers and simplifying the orchestration of large-scale multi-cloud infrastructures, albeit requiring a high level of knowledge for efficient infrastructure management. Complementing Terraform's resource creation functionality, there are typically configuration tools such as Ansible [STCN15].

This automation can be coordinated in an additional layer known as GitOps [BH22], which adds automatic deployment through DevOps management and distributed version control tools like Git. An example of the power of this approach can be found in event management services on platforms like GitHub or GitLab.

6GENABLERS-AI aims to acquire new knowledge and zero-touch techniques for the deployment and orchestration of 5G resources. The programmatic and automatic approach to deploying and configuring edge clusters to manage 5G resources requires a declarative definition to express various configurations of edge clusters that are valid for different provider profiles and locations, as well as integrations with 5G. It is also necessary to have the ability to define the architecture and technologies that enable infrastructure connectivity in a programmatic way with a unified platform, including resources from currently separate and heterogeneous domains. These advancements will represent a significant transformation in the management of 5G resources and networks in distributed cloud-edge environments.

2. State of the Art on Zero-Touch Networks

This section describes the state of the art on Zero-Touch networks covering three main aspects, namely: network management, AI operations and low-latency applications.

2.1. Automatic Infrastructure Discovery and Deployment

5G/6G Zero-Touch Networks (ZSM) represent a revolutionary paradigm shift in networking, where autonomous, self-configuring, and self-optimizing networks are realized. Edge computing has gained prominence as a fundamental component of ZSM networks, enabling efficient resource allocation and dynamic service provisioning (e.g. VNFs) at the network's edge. Edge infrastructure discovery is a crucial aspect of ZSM, ensuring that the right resources are available when and where they are needed. There are many works focused on resource discovery in IoT environments [Goud22]. Resource discovery in cloud and multi-cloud environments has also been explored in several works. For example, [Moor20] proposes a clustering-based method called SCAK-Means for discovering cloud resources that satisfy the user request. [Sharm21] presents BIRD, a Blockchain-based Intercloud Resource Discovery framework that involves participating cloud service providers connected in a P2P network using blockchain to manage resource information and maintain transactional records. Also, some works have explored the resource discovery problem on edge computing environments, for example, [Murt22] introduces a decentralized mechanism that enables edge devices to connect in a P2P manner, organize edge devices in clusters, and support automatic discovery of heterogeneous resources in edge networks. [Gaut22] proposes a location discovery mechanism that considers hop-distance and eliminates redundant nodes for density computation in the process of optimal location identification. A mapping scheme is proposed named a Minimum Set Assignment First that minimizes the difference of mapped nodes among edge nodes. Verizon [Veri22] has also deployed a 5G Edge Discovery Service for Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) applications which allows application clients to connect to the optimal service endpoints. This Edge Discovery Service takes into account the current location of a device, its IP anchor location, current network traffic, and other factors to select the best 5G Edge platform a device should connect to. A major limitation of these discovery mechanisms is that they are not suitable for large-scale, geo-distributed and heterogeneous edge computing platforms, as used in 5G/6G zero-touch networks and services.

The deployment of 5G/6G ZSM networks and services on top of cloud and edge computing infrastructures is supported by two major technologies: VNF (Virtualized Network Function) and SDN (Software Defined Network). For example, regarding network slicing management [Bory20, Sing22, Srin23], VNFs can be used to orchestrate the creation, modification, and deletion of network slices, and help in managing the lifecycle of network slices, ensuring the efficient allocation of resources and adherence to service-level agreements (SLAs). On the other hand, SDN controllers are used to dynamically route traffic for different network slices, and provide centralized control over network resources, allowing for efficient and dynamic allocation of bandwidth and connectivity paths for various slices. VNF and SDN technologies are also involved in the management of cloud-RAN in 5G and beyond networks [Rost17, Ibnk21, Angu22]. In this context, Virtualized Radio Functions (vRAN) can replace traditional dedicated hardware at cell sites. Functions such as baseband processing and radio resource management are virtualized as VNFs. This centralization leads to resource efficiency, as VNFs can be shared among multiple cells or sectors, reducing hardware costs and energy

consumption. In addition, SDN controllers can dynamically allocate network resources, including bandwidth and routing paths, to support vRAN functions based on real-time demand. This ensures efficient resource utilization and minimizes latency, contributing to improved performance.

In this context, the efficient and intelligent orchestration of geographically distributed edge-cloud infrastructures to facilitate the automated management, placement, and scaling of VNFs and SDNs for 5G/6G networks emerges as a pivotal factor in advancing zero-touch network and service development.

2.2. AI-enabled Edge Orchestration

In the literature, we can find numerous works that employ AI techniques, including evolutionary algorithms and ML algorithms, to solve various prediction and optimization problems in Cloud and Edge environments. For instance, a recent study [Khan22a] provides a detailed review of machine learning-based resource management solutions, covering workload estimation, task scheduling, VM consolidation, resource optimization, and energy efficiency techniques, among others. Additionally, a recent book [Gupt22] compiles several research works on optimal resource allocation, energy efficiency, and predictive models in cloud computing, utilizing different ML techniques, such as deep learning or neural networks.

Focused on workload prediction, this is an essential technique in cloud computing environments as it enables providers to effectively manage and allocate cloud resources, save infrastructure costs, implement auto-scaling policies, and ensure compliance with service level agreements (SLAs) with users. Workload prediction can be performed at the application or infrastructure level. Application-level techniques [Lian14, More19a] involve predicting a metric related to the application demand (e.g., requests per second or task arrival rate) to anticipate the optimal number of resources needed to meet that demand. On the other hand, infrastructure-level techniques [Mehm18, ALAs21] are based on predicting one or more resource usage metrics (such as CPU, memory, disk, or network) and making advanced decisions about the optimal number and size of VMs or physical resources to provision to avoid overload or over-sizing situations. Another interesting work in this area is [Asla20], which presents a taxonomy of the various real-world metrics to evaluate the performance of cloud, fog, and edge computing environments.

The most common workload prediction techniques used in cloud computing are based on time-series prediction methods [Masd20, Devi23], which involve collecting historical data of the target metric (e.g., the historical CPU usage of a VM or group of VMs) and forecasting future values of that metric for a certain time horizon. There are many different methods for modeling and predicting time-series used in cloud computing, many of them based on classical techniques such as linear regressions [Yang13], Bayesian models [DiKo12], or ARIMA statistical methods [Calh15]. The main advantage of these models is their flexibility and simplicity in representing different types of time-series, making them quick and easy to use. However, they have a significant limitation due to their linear behavior, making them inadequate in some practical situations.

More recently, different methods have been proposed for time-series prediction based on machine learning and deep learning models [AIAs21, Khan22b, Nawr21] using artificial neural networks that have inherent non-linear modeling capabilities. One of the most common ML

models applied to time-series is the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network [GaoW20, BiLiZ21, Chen22], which overcomes the problem of vanishing gradients associated with other neural networks. However, these methods also have several drawbacks. The first is that the training and prediction times of the neural network can be quite high (several minutes, even hours), making them unfeasible in certain situations. The second problem is that the quality of predictions from neural network-based methods depends heavily on the correct selection of the model's hyperparameters, which can vary depending on the input data, making adjusting these hyperparameters a serious challenge even for expert analysts.

In absolute terms, it is not possible to claim that one prediction method is better than another, as their behavior will depend on the specific use case, the profile of the input data, the correct tuning of each model's hyperparameters, or the use or non-use of co-variables that may have correlation with the variable being predicted. In this context, research in this field involves exploring and comparing different prediction methods for each case, improving existing methods, and combining different techniques by proposing new hybrid or adaptive methods that allow for the most accurate forecasts possible. Likewise, applying these prediction techniques to other emerging environments such as highly geo-distributed edge/cloud environments, IoT environments, or zero-touch networks and services deployment, also represents a significant challenge.

On the other hand, the optimal allocation of resources in cloud computing is an important problem that must be addressed to ensure efficient use of resources and meet agreed SLAs with users. The goal is to allocate resources (e.g. VMs to physical hosts) in a way that maximizes infrastructure utilization, subject to certain performance or application response time requirements.

There are different optimization techniques used to solve this problem. One of the most commonly used techniques is linear programming [Rezv15, Entr21], which finds the optimal solution to a set of linear equations subject to certain constraints. Nonetheless, the computational demands of linear programming increase significantly as the number of variables and constraints grows. For very large problems, this approach might become computationally expensive and time-consuming. Other techniques used are heuristic optimization techniques based on bio-inspired algorithms [Abba20, Deva21, Luzh22, XiaS21, Prad22], such as genetic algorithms, PSO (Particle Swarm Optimization), ACO (Ant Colony Optimization), etc. These algorithms allow finding suboptimal solutions for optimization problems that are too complex to solve exactly. Genetic algorithms, for example, are inspired by natural selection and biological evolution to find optimal solutions. Reinforcement learning is another technique that has been successfully used in resource management and allocation in cloud computing [Wang21, Jian21, Humm22]. This technique is based on a learning model in which an agent interacts with an environment and receives a reward or punishment based on its actions. Through experience, the agent learns to make optimal decisions that maximize expected reward.

Each technique has its advantages and disadvantages, and the choice of the most appropriate technique will depend on the specific characteristics of the problem to be solved. In general, linear programming is more suitable for well-structured problems with a limited number of variables and constraints. Metaheuristic algorithms are more suitable for more complex problems with a large number of variables and constraints. Reinforcement learning, on the other hand, is more suitable for problems involving uncertainty and changes in the environment. Sometimes it will also be necessary to address multi-objective problems, where it is necessary

to optimize more than one objective function subject to certain constraints. Research in this field involves exploring, analyzing, and comparing different optimization techniques adapted to each problem and use case, including the treatment of both single and multi-objective problems and the possibility of combining different techniques through the proposal of new hybrid optimization techniques. Furthermore, the application of these optimization techniques to other emerging environments such as highly geo-distributed edge/cloud environments, IoT environments or zero-touch networks and services deployment, also represents an important challenge.

There are also several research works focused on AI-driven resource management (e.g., VNFs) for 5G/6G edge infrastructures and ZSM environments. In this context, [Gall22] presents a compelling survey on ML techniques that are being currently exploited to build further ZSM developments, regarding different aspects, including multi-tenancy management, traffic monitoring, and architecture coordination, among others. [Atta23] also analyzes several works on VNF and CNF (Container Network Functions) placement in 5G. It classifies the optimization techniques based on different performance metrics, methods, algorithms, and environment, and analyzes different placement techniques based on heuristics, meta-heuristics, and ML algorithms.

With the 5G-PPP initiative, the white paper [Kalo20] also explores the main relevant mechanisms in AI and ML currently investigated and exploited for 5G and B5G networks, and identifies solutions pertaining to AI-based autonomous slice management, control and orchestration, AI/ML-based scaling operations in network service orchestration, AI/ML as a Service in network management and orchestration, enablement of ML for the verticals' domain, cross-layer optimization, management analytics in general, 3rd party ML analytics for network operation optimization in particular, anomaly detection using AI/ML.

Other remarkable research contributions in this area are [Waha19], which proposes a ML-based clustering approach named MAPLE that divides the substrate network into a set of disjoint clusters, to reduce the complexity of VNF placement and adjustment, then they model the VNF placement and readjustment problem as an ILP problem which considers a trade-off among the minimization of the latency, Service-Level Objective (SLO) violation cost, hardware resource utilization, and VNF readjustment cost. [EmuY20] presents an Integer Linear Programming model to solve the optimal edge VNF placement problem, focusing on minimizing end-to-end latency and maintaining Quality of Service by not exceeding acceptable latency limits. As this algorithm is NP-hard and not suitable for large problems, they further propose an Artificial Neural Network (ANN)-based solution trained with ILP-generated assignment solutions for smaller VNF instances. This approach efficiently addresses VNF assignments at edge devices for a higher number of VNFs, reducing time complexity to linear levels while maintaining low latency levels, akin to the ILP model.

[Mendo22] studies the problem of placing VNFs in edge computing-enabled 6G networks, with the objective of placing the VNFs in the different edge nodes of the network to minimize the rejection ratio of the requests. They develop a practical solution to the problem using Reinforcement Learning (RL), where the problem is treated with Q-Learning that considers both computational and communication resources when placing VNFs in the network. One of the main limitations of these works is that they are not focussed on highly geo-distributed edge platforms supported by upcoming 5G/6G networks.

2.3. Low-Latency Edge Services

There is extensive research on latency-sensitive applications in Edge computing. For example, in [Mahe18], the performance of a city-scale Edge system designed to run latency-sensitive applications is analyzed. A low-latency video analytics Edge computing platform has also been introduced in [YiHa17], as well as a lightweight Fog Computing-based system for cloud gaming [LiSh17]. In this context, OpenNebula provides a disaggregated Cloud architecture for Edge Computing [More19b], which has been experimentally validated for various use cases such as IoT or FPS (First Person Shooter) Massive Multiplayer Online Games [Hued21]. Another interesting work in this area is EdgeFlow [Avas22], a IoT framework for assisting the development and deployment of latency-sensitive IoT applications on edge environments. For the development stage, they propose a flow-based programming paradigm that enables the developer to provide timing and resource requirements for applications. For the deployment stage, they introduce a resource allocation technique capable of finding optimal or feasible deployment strategies that satisfies the previous requirements. Other interesting works on edge resource allocation for low-latency services are [Abou21], which presents an optimization method to dynamically allocate resources on edge devices based on latency, or [Pane22], which proposes a framework for ensuring efficient edge relocation of latency-sensitive edge applications, in order to support service continuity.

Regarding the deployment of 5G/6G edge services for low and ultra-low latency applications, an interesting review is presented in [Hass19]. This work analyzes the main objectives of edge computing in 5G networks, including the improvement of data management to handle a large amount of delay-sensitive data, the improvement of QoS to meet a diverse range of stringent QoS requirements in order to improve quality of experience (QoE), the prediction of network demand to estimate the required network resources, and subsequently to provide optimal resource allocation to handle the local network demand, the management of location awareness to enable the geographically distributed edge servers to infer their own locations and track the location of end users to support location-based services, and the improvement of resource management to optimize network resource utilization for network performance enhancement due to the limited network resources available in the edge as compared to the cloud. Currently, many of these challenges are still to be solved.

Another interesting work is [Rahi21], where authors propose an architectural model for edge computing in 5G and beyond that takes advantage of novel and sustainable technologies (e.g., D2D communication, Massive MIMO, SDN, and NFV) and has major features such as scalability, reliability, and ultra-low latency support. In [Gupt21], authors analyze the advantages of edge computing over cloud computing to overcome latency and reliability issues in critical applications, and explore the potential of 6G in edge intelligence networks. They present a 6G-enabled edge intelligence architecture by considering various applications such as AVs, Internet of drones, and holographic communication. Furthermore, they also analyze some interesting challenges concerning efficient edge resource allocation, data security, support for complex intelligence algorithms at edge nodes, and communication and synchronization among edge services.

3. Requirement Analysis

This section includes an analysis of requirements from the project use case and Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) ETSI reports related to cloud-edge infrastructure automatic deployment (A2.1) and service orchestration (A2.2).

The section will include both functional and non-functional requirements for a ZSM framework reference architecture.

3.1. Project Use Case Requirements

Table 1. Project use case non-functional requirements

Requirement	Type	Description
NFR1 - Scalability	Non-functional requirements	The implementation of the holoportation use case should be scalable and allow for the automatic admission of multiple concurrent AR users/sessions/slices without modifying the architecture.
NFR2 - Interoperability	Non-functional requirements	The setup of the holoportation use case should be interoperable with any type of user device/AR kit
NFR3 - Modularity	Non-functional requirements	The implementation of the holoportation use case should be modular to a great extent in such a way the upgrade of one component can be independently done without affecting the other components.
NFR4 - High-performance computing	Non-functional requirements	Holoportation generates and consumes tremendous amounts of data that need to be processed at run-time before or after their transmission or even on their way to the destination.
NFR5 - Low latency	Non-functional requirements	Holoportation is highly interactive and hence requires high-precision, predictable and ultra-low latency.
NFR6 - High bandwidth	Non-functional requirements	Holoportation applications need to transmit tremendous amounts of data that can go from a few tens of megabytes to terabytes of data per second.

Table 2. Project use case functional requirements

Requirement	Type	Description
FR1 - Bandwidth adaptability	Functional requirements	Holoportation requires high uplink and downlink bandwidth and stringent adaptability requirements
FR2 - Specific protocols	Functional requirements	Holoportation requires the use of specialized protocols for the transmission and rendering of 3D models
FR3 - Synchronization	Functional requirements	Holoportation may require multiple flows to be synchronized (i.e., multi-flow synchronization), that is to ensure that the generated data from different sources arrive at the destination within a specific interval of time or even at a particular point of time.
FR4 - Automated network slicing management	Functional requirements	Dynamic and automated network management and slicing will enable the adaptation of network service characteristics to the application needs (e.g. specific protocols, bandwidth requirements, latency requirements, synchronization requirements, etc.)
FR5 - VNF placement	Functional requirements	By placing holographic service's VNFs (encoding, reconstruction, fusion, frame alignment...) closer to the holograms source, the amount of data that needs to be transmitted across the different technological domains—i.e., RAN, Edge and Cloud—is reduced, leading to lower latency and improved network performance.
FR6 - VNF autoscaling	Functional requirements	VNF autoscaling will allow to reduce the reaction time (e.g. potential changes in the conditions of the holographic-type communication or the arrival of new monitoring data)
FR7 - AI-based predictive modeling	Functional requirements	Resource allocation and optimization (e.g VNFs) depends on the accuracy of predicting the resource and task requirements.
FR8 - AI-based optimization	Functional requirements	VNF placement and autoscaling could require optimization for multiple objectives such as minimizing latency, maximizing throughput, and minimizing resource utilization. Traditional optimization methods (e.g. ILP) or AI-based optimization methods can be used to address this problem.
FR9 - Intelligent orchestration	Functional requirements	Intelligent orchestration techniques must be able to adapt to changing workloads and resource requirements in real-time, ensuring that the system continues to operate effectively.

3.2. Relationship with the ETSI ZSM Framework

ETSI [ZSM-reqs] defines 39 scenarios grouped in different categories (and sub-categories) outlining the importance and emphasis of topics such as the management and operation of network slicing in 5G networks, the Network as a Service model, the use and integration of machine learning techniques for network management and operation, collaborative or federated service management, security, testing, tracing, and other important topics like integration and interoperation.

176 requirements are derived from the documented scenarios. The requirements are assigned to different categories. Some of these requirements are further refined and broken down into multiple functional and non-functional requirements in other documents.

ETSI [ZSM-arc] defines a reference architecture for the ZSM framework, which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Reference architecture of the ETSI ZSM framework [ZSM-arc]

In the above architecture, OpenNebula would fit in a Management Domain, providing virtual, physical and Cloud resource deployment and management. According to ETSI [ZSM-arq], *“Management domains federate together management services with capabilities needed to manage resource-facing services or resources within a given domain .../... Each management domain manages one or more entities, such as infrastructure resources and/or resource-facing services associated with the management domain. Infrastructure resources can be physical (e.g. physical network functions (PNFs)), virtual (e.g. virtualized network functions (VNFs)) or software-based services) and/or cloud based (e.g. “X-as-a-service” (XaaS) resources)”*.

ETSI [ZSM-arq] identifies general requirements for the ZSM framework reference architecture related to availability, compliance, energy efficiency, QoS, interoperability, determinism, standardisation and security, to which OpenNebula can significantly contribute to its fulfillment. In addition to this, OpenNebula will directly provide capabilities mainly for Domain Data Collection, Domain Control and Domain Orchestration to be integrated in the ZSM framework.

According to ETSI [ZSM-arq], *“The domain data collection services monitor the managed entities and consumed managed services and provide e.g. live performance and fault data to support closed-loop automation, which needs to be able to verify how the network reacts to changes (such as optimization)”*.

Domain data collection provides the following services:

- Event notification services
- Performance measurements streaming service
- Performance measurements collection service
- Log collection service

According to ETSI [ZSM-arq], *“Domain control services allow to individually steer the state of each managed entity. The service producers which provide domain control services consume for example the configuration management interfaces provided by the managed entities and abstract from their service consumers the details of configuration changes. As an example, the domain control services can be consumed by management functions that offer services in the domain orchestration group to change the state or configuration of a managed entity and consumed service. The domain control group may also contain services that are needed to control virtualized resources”*.

Domain control provides the following services:

- Resource configuration management service
- Resource lifecycle management services
- Configuration data generation service

According to ETSI [ZSM-arq], *“Domain orchestration provides management services that allow automating workflows and processes inside a management domain to handle lifecycle management of the managed customer and/or resource-facing services. Domain orchestration services maintain the inventory of network services and virtualized resources managed by the management domain and an up-to-date view of the related topology, by using discovery, inventory and topology management services. Domain orchestration is controlled by policies and other additional relevant information sources, e.g. SLAs”*.

Domain orchestration provides the following services:

- Domain orchestration service
- Feasibility check service
- Managed services catalogue management service
- Testing service
- Domain inventory information service
- Domain inventory management service
- Domain topology information service

Finally, OpenNebula will provide support for Domain Analytics and Domain Intelligence [ZSM-arq], enabling the implementation of Closed-Loop Automation and Artificial Intelligence-based Network and Service Automation. Since these capabilities are strongly dependent on the service, OpenNebula will not offer them directly, but will support external modules implementing them. For example, if we consider the MAPE-K (Monitor-Analyse-Plan-Execute plus Knowledge) model for self-adaptive systems, OpenNebula will provide support for implementing the Monitor and Execute steps, and similarly for other similar models, like OODA (Observe, Orient, Decide and Act) or MRACL (Model-Reference Adaptive Control Loop).

4. Gap Analysis

This section describes the gaps within the current state-of-the-art technologies, as described in Section 2, aiming to meet the requirements of zero-touch networks as outlined in Section 3. It's important to note that this Section does not include an exhaustive list of gaps but to analyze those specific gaps the project will tackle.

4.1. Automatic Infrastructure Discovery and Deployment

The first step needed to achieve a zero-touch system is the ability to automate its deployment. In the context of the project this means the ability to deploy edge locations close to the user equipment (UE) to minimize latency between the clients and the data processing elements.

Usually the automatic deployment involves three different steps, namely:

- **Infrastructure discovery.** Usually the infrastructure is deployed in the location where the client is connected to. In that case, the discovery and selection of the edge locations is straightforward. However we are considering a dynamic selection of locations to also support more advanced scenarios where various components of the pipeline are distributed across different points in the edge-cloud continuum. For example, the decoding and decompression part of the AR pipeline may be located in a cloud node to stream the scene to multiple clients; or to provide some level of redundancy for some components of the AR pipeline.
- **Infrastructure provision.** Once the locations that are going to be used for deploying the components of the holoportation pipeline are selected, it may be necessary to provision the computational resources. This is especially the case when using a cloud-edge provider.
- **Infrastructure configuration.** The final step consists of configuring the resources, the virtualization and storage services, as well as any network overlay (e.g. VPN) to interconnect the elements of the distributed holoportation pipeline.

The main challenge arises from the inherently distributed nature of the holoportation application which spawns multiple locations in the cloud-edge continuum. The automatic deployment and configuration of such infrastructures needs to develop robust selection algorithms for the edge-cloud locations, as well as the orchestration capabilities needed to deploy a complex system in an autonomous manner.

4.2. AI-enabled Edge Orchestration

Another important feature of a “zero touch” system is its intrinsic capacity for self-healing and self-adjustment, driven by the analysis of the information gathered from systemic activities. Ideally, the network should act autonomously on the early detection of problems, the remediation of such issues and the optimization of the overall performance of the applications. The following gaps needs to be addressed:

- **Workload Optimization.** The ZSM needs to integrate multiple information sources to optimize the performance of the holoportation application, including: application metrics, server information, network data or provider response times. Note that the introspection

capabilities of each part of the systems varies (e.g. the information of cloud providers may be limited or need to be derived from other sources). The overall information will be used by AI enabled module to:

- Predict the workload profile
 - Optimize the placement of the holoportation components
 - Dynamically set elasticity rules for autonomous self-elasticity.
- **Anomaly detection.** The AI module integrated into the system must demonstrate the capability to identify potential anomalous conditions compromising the performance of the application or the integrity of the system. In the event of anomaly detection, the system is expected to respond proactively, potentially by reconfiguring segments of the pipeline (e.g., migrating specific components) or generating new instances in alternative locations.

5. Proposed Cloud-Edge 5G Architecture

This section describes the architecture of a Cloud-Edge system designed for edge applications. The system is presented in a generic form to accommodate a wide range of applications with strong latency requirements. The overall architecture aligns with the requirements discussed in Section 2, and it is compatible with the zero touch network and service management (ZSM) framework under development by the ETSI organization, see section above.

5.1. Distributed System Components

The Cloud-Edge 5G (CE5G) architecture is a highly distributed system that spawns across multiple network locations to enable the deployment of low-latency applications. CE5G includes elements to orchestrate and maintain the entire system lifecycle, from the physical infrastructure to the application. CE5G exhibits the following high level characteristics, see Figure 2:

- Multiple edge locations. In order to minimize the latency across application components they must be placed close to the client locations. In this way, most of the application processing happens at the edge of the network reducing the traffic across components.
- Common orchestration facilities. The applications are delivered following an as-a-service paradigm. Consequently, the application is automatically provisioned in the required location and its life-cycle is managed by a common orchestration layer. This encompasses not only the application components themselves but also the edge infrastructure and any supporting services (e.g. network functions)
- Distributed application. In general, a distributed application requires the deployment of multiple components usually in the form of virtual machines or containers. For example, the holoportation use-case is modeled as an augmented reality (AR) pipeline with multiple components (e.g. synchronization, or multi-sensor fusion) each one deployed in one or more edge locations to optimize performance and minimize latency.

Considering these main three elements we can identify 3 relevant network segments, namely:

- 5G radio link. In this segment, clients establish network connections via a 5G network. This component embodies the radio access network, extending from user equipment to the base station situated in the edge location.
- Edge node network. It represents the network that interconnects all the components in the edge node, including the Local Area Network (LAN) that interconnects the Edge servers, alongside any overlay networks facilitating intercommunication among application components.
- Backbone. It represents the Internet that interconnects each Edge location.

The rest of the section describes with some detail each of the components of the CE5G architecture.

5.1.1 Bare Metal and Operating System Services

The processing power capabilities of the system is provided by the bare metal services in each Edge location. The servers run applications in some form of virtualization, either Virtual Machines (VM) or applications containers. In this proposed architecture, VMs serve as the foundational management unit. It is worth noting that containerized applications can be seamlessly deployed via a virtualized container service, such as a virtual Kubernetes cluster.

In addition to the core Operating System (OS) and virtualization infrastructure (in our case, KVM), VMs leverage a software switch, OpenvSwitch, to establish connections within the Edge network and implement specific flow policies or network overlays.

5.1.2 Cloud Orchestrator

CE5G employs OpenNebula as its primary orchestration component. OpenNebula is an open-source cloud platform that offers advanced orchestration functionalities for virtualized infrastructures. Within the CE5G framework, OpenNebula is responsible for deploying and managing the virtualized AR pipelines in the selected Edge locations. Additionally, OpenNebula takes on the responsibility of deploying any associated elements, including virtual networks, using its internal Software-Defined Networking (SDN) capabilities. OpenNebula also provides the multitenancy and isolation layer needed to ensure that multiple AR pipelines can coexist in the system.

5.1.3 Artificial Intelligence Operations (AIOps)

In the dynamic landscape of Cloud-Edge 5G (CE5G), Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays an important role in optimizing the system's performance. The AIOps component is responsible for

the optimal placement of the application selecting the most suitable Edge locations. The AIOps component uses real-time monitoring information to minimize latency, maximize resource utilization, and ensure the efficient distribution of workloads. By analyzing this data, AI can predict and prevent potential issues before they impact service quality. It can detect anomalies in the network, assess performance trends, and proactively address bottlenecks or failures.

AIOps relies on a monitoring infrastructure to acquire essential performance data necessary for forecasting system behavior and optimizing performance. CE5G uses Prometheus¹, an open source monitoring toolkit featuring time series databases with a flexible query language. Prometheus periodically scrapes monitoring data from several sources, in particular we will combine 3 different sources:

- **Bare metal server** information, using the standard Prometheus node-exporter module. This module gathers multiple metrics from hardware devices and software services of a Linux OS.
- **Virtual Machine** performance metrics, using OpenNebula libvirt exporter. This module provides information about KVM domains using the libvirtd API.
- **Cloud** metrics, using OpenNebula exporter. This module includes overall information of the status of the cloud and edge locations.

AIOps leverages Prometheus data to proactively anticipate system and workload performance issues. Specifically, diverse predictive intelligence techniques will be evaluated for forecasting both virtual and physical system metrics (such as CPU usage, memory usage, or bandwidth consumption) and application workload metrics. These predictive methods encompass time-series forecasting approaches, including classical techniques like linear regressions, Bayesian models, or ARIMA statistical methods, as well as machine learning and deep learning models, such as LSTM and N-BEATS [Ores20].

These predictions will serve as a foundation for optimizing resource orchestration or detecting metric anomalies. Addressing resource orchestration involves determining the optimal mapping or distribution of virtual resources (VMs or containers) across available edge servers. This process relies on various optimization criteria, including reducing infrastructure costs, minimizing energy consumption, optimizing application latency or response time, or minimizing data movement. Evaluation and comparison of different scheduling techniques for virtual resource allocation and migration will be conducted, such as integer linear programming (ILP)-based optimization techniques and heuristic-based scheduling algorithms.

Conversely, in the context of metric anomaly detection, diverse unsupervised time series forecasting methods [Schm22] will be explored, where the anomalous nature of observed values in the original time series is determined by comparing them with the forecasted data points. These methods encompass traditional statistical techniques (e.g., ARIMA), machine learning methods (e.g., random forest), and deep learning methods (e.g., LSTM).

5.1.4 Automated Resource Provision

In order to deploy and operate such a complex system, a high degree of automation is required. CE5G features an automated resource provision module to provision and configure Edge locations. Given that these locations often operate with resource constraints, Edge locations

¹ Prometheus web site <https://prometheus.io/>, retrieved November 2023.

require the use of hyper-convergent solutions. Given the diverse nature of Edge locations, the automation module interfaces with multiple providers. This enables coverage of a broader spectrum of Edge locations, each potentially offered by different service providers.

Figure 3 describes the main components of the provisioning components of CE5G. The Automated provision module orchestrates three different aspects to provision Edge locations, namely:

- **Provision** of the Edge location resources. In order to interface different providers CE5G uses the common abstraction layer provided by Terraform². This allows CE5G to use different providers, but also private data centers located at the edge of the network.
- **Configuration** of the Edge resources. Once provisioned the edge resources need to be prepared by installing and configuring the required virtualization services. This automatic configuration is performed with specific Ansible³ playbooks. This also enables CE5G to develop specific Edge location flavors to accommodate different Edge configurations.
- Cloud **management** of Edge resources. Once provisioned and configured, the Edge location needs to be registered in the Cloud management system, so they can be used to deploy 5G applications.

5.1.5 Application Management

In the context of CE5G, an application is defined as a cohesive set of Virtual Machines (VMs) that collectively serve a particular purpose or workflow. The workflow encapsulates the required software components, configurations, and dependencies necessary to deliver specific services. The OpenNebula Flow engine is responsible for deploying and managing this application workflow.

² Terraform web site <https://www.terraform.io/>, retrieved November 2023.

³ Ansible web site <https://www.ansible.com/>, retrieved November 2023

To streamline the deployment of applications, CE5G features a marketplace featuring a catalog of predefined services and application templates. This marketplace offers a repository of pre-configured application stacks, allowing users to select, customize, and deploy applications with ease. The AR pipeline mentioned before is formulated as an OpenNebula Flow available in the CE5G marketplace.

5.2. The 5G Edge Node Architecture

The Edge Node within the CE5G framework is the main element that supports the execution of the low-latency edge applications. This Section describes the main aspects of the Edge Node, depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 4. High level overview of the 5G Edge Node Architecture

At the core of the Edge Node is the 5G Network, which connects the CE5G applications to the user equipment (UE). The Edge Node does not have direct control over the orchestration module of the RAN. Usually a 5G Core also runs at the node to manage functions such as authentication, session management and network slicing.

The 5G network components, and any other virtualized network function (VNF) like virtual routers, are deployed on the node servers. In order to achieve low-latency and maximize the performance delivered to these components, they are usually pinned to a set of CPU cores and NUMA nodes. This also allows the efficient sharing of CPU resources across different applications (e.g. different AR pipelines). Furthermore, certain application components (*Data Processing* block in Figure 4, see also Section 6 for a detailed description) may require direct

access to the network interfaces or GPU cards. The OpenNebula orchestrator takes charge of the NUMA pinning allocation and SR-IOV passthrough of devices as needed.

Applications are typically delivered as a set of VMs (see section 4.1.5) and deployed by the OpenNebula Flow service. However, CE5G also accommodates the deployment of applications as containerized services. In such cases, CE5G leverages virtualized Kubernetes clusters to manage the deployment and operation of these containerized components.

6. Use Case Deployment and KPIs

In this Section we discuss the deployment of holographic teleportation applications in the CE5G architecture described above. We consider a generic Augmented Reality (AR) pipeline that consists on five stages [ShGa23]:

- **Data Capture.** This stage involves the use of cameras and various sensors to capture scenes at the client side, which are subsequently transmitted remotely. It's important to note that the User Equipment (UE) responsible for data capture operates independently of the CE5G system.
- **Data Processing.** It refers to general processing of the data captured by the UE. It includes: the synchronization of multiple flows from different sources, encoding and compression of the resulting 3D models
- **Transmission,** the resulting data is then streamed to the remote edge nodes via Internet links.
- **Decoding and Decompression.** Upon reaching the target location, the received data is decoded, decompressed, and formatted suitably for reproduction.
- **Rendering & Display.** The final phase comprises the rendering transmitted scene on compatible AR/VR devices. It's worth noting that the processing undertaken by these UEs is not within the control of the CE5G system.

In order to deploy such application, CE5G will follow these steps:

- **Edge Node Allocation:** The initial step involves allocating and preparing Edge Nodes by configuring a cluster of edge servers. These resources are registered within the orchestrator, enabling the deployment of edge applications
- **Application Deployment:** The AR processing pipeline is modeled as a workflow application, where the Data Processing and Decoding and Decompression phases are allocated to two distinct Virtual Machines (VMs) located in the producing and consuming Edge Nodes, respectively. Concurrently, additional monitoring components are deployed to oversee the status of the pipeline.
- **VNF Integration:** Optionally, the AR pipeline may incorporate Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) to construct overlays across the participating edge nodes, further enhancing the functionality of the holographic application.
- **AIOps Monitoring:** The AIOps module assumes the crucial role of analyzing real-time data generated by the pipeline components. It uses this data to predict and proactively address performance issues, ensuring the seamless operation of the AR pipeline. As previously noted in Section 5.1.3, this module encompasses a range of techniques, including predictive intelligence applied to system and application metrics, optimal resource orchestration methods, and unsupervised time series forecasting techniques for anomaly detection.

Table 3 describes the KPIs considered in the deployment of the use case. The KPIs refers to the *zero-touch* deployment of the holoportation pipeline (KPI-CE5G-1) and the AIOps module (KPI-CE5G-2). These two KPI's align with the two main gaps described in Section 4, automatic infrastructure discovery and AI operations, respectively.

Table 3. KPIs for the Cloud-Edge 5G system

Description	Target	Reference
Deployment time of the use case	Edge locations, network and app components has to be deployed in less than 1 hour using two different locations	KPI-CE5G-1
Model optimization iteration time	The iteration time of the AI models has to be performed in less than 1 hour.	KPI-CE5G-2

7. Conclusion

This report has analyzed the state and presented the functional and system requirements related to intelligent and zero-touch network management from the perspective of the underlying edge infrastructure enabling technology, and the support of an automated, intelligent, end-to-end management paradigm in the evolution towards 5G/6G networks. The deliverable has covered aspects related to functional validation that will demonstrate the capability of zero-touch management and the verification of results in a medium-scale proof of concept. The main objective has been to identify deficiencies in existing methods and derive the set of functional and non-functional requirements that will drive the specifications of the system architecture in terms of intelligent management. It also provides information on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be validated during the validation phase.

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